

*Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.*

Deliverable Title: **D3.2 Framework for RRI implementation in R&I ecosystems of the three territories**

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Description of the deliverable (3-6 lines)	The deliverable presents a general framework for how to incorporate RRI into the digitalization process of traditional industry territories. The framework is intended for territories that have adopted a smart specialization strategy (S3). The framework highlights RRI-related challenges and opportunities arising from digitalization.
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DEFINITIONS

Main concepts	Definition
Digitalized industry territories	Territories with a high level of digitalization in their industrial sectors, i.e. a high level of digital development and usage of ICT innovations, taking into account technical, business as well as social elements (see e.g., Grundke et al., 2018).
Quadruple Helix	The quadruple helix model of innovation adds a fourth component to the framework of the triple helix model: the public, consisting of civil society and the media (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009).
RRI	Responsible research and innovation (RRI) is defined as an inclusive approach to R&I, to ensure that societal actors work together to better align both the processes and outcomes of R&I, with the values, needs and expectations of the society. The concept originated from the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) around 2011 and has been widely used since then in European R&I policy, especially as a cross-cutting issue in the EU’s Horizon 2020 programme (Owen et al., 2012).
R&I ecosystem	Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystems are represented by a complex interplay between academic and business actors as well as the public sector and being connected in networks of research, development and innovation activities supported by public policy mechanisms (Tondelli et al., 2019).
Territory	A territory is defined as any geographical area characterized by certain geographical features, or shared cultural, environmental, or economic ties (Magnaghi, 2005).

Source: Paier et al. (2020).

ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial intelligence
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and communications technology
IoT	Internet of things
IPR	Intellectual property rights
MLP	Multi-level perspective
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
R&D	Research and development
R&I	Research and innovation
RIS3	Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
4H	Quadruple Helix

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents a non-region-specific framework for regional digitalization under consideration of RRI principles. The framework will serve two main purposes in DigiTeRRI. First, it will help to create a shared understanding among territories and partners in the project about roadmapping methodology, regional transition processes, and the relationship between RRI and digitalization. Second, it will be used in communicating with the stakeholders in regional workshops about the roadmapping process and how to take RRI into account in digitalization.

The common framework introduced in this report consists of two parts. In the first part we explain DigiTeRRI's roadmapping methodology at a conceptual level, setting the stage for creating actual roadmaps in the three pilot territories of DigiTeRRI in WP4. In the second part we describe at a non-region-specific level how the transition from a traditional industry region to a digitalized region creates challenges and opportunities for practicing RRI.

The main DigiTeRRI roadmap process is based on a classical roadmap process and is composed of four phases: stocktaking and mapping; visioning; roadmap development; and roadmap implementation and improvement. The methodology revolves around co-creation with stakeholders, and therefore achieving a common understanding among the participating stakeholders with respect to the overall process and the analytical frame is an essential prerequisite for success. Throughout the roadmapping process, DigiTeRRI integrates the major process dimensions of RRI: diversity and inclusiveness; anticipation and reflexivity; openness and transparency; and responsiveness and adaptivity. The roadmapping process generates action plans for each of the four types of stakeholders that together compose the “quadruple helix”: government, academia, industry, and civil society.

The second part of the framework analyses the relationship between RRI and digitalization, focusing for simplicity on the contrast between the extreme endpoints of digitalization, i.e. “low” digitalization (traditional industry) and “high” digitalization (fully digitalized R&I ecosystem). This part of the framework shows how RRI opportunities and challenges change as regions and the organizations within them are transformed from a non-digital to a digital state of development. The analysis is structured by the five RRI “keys” highlighted by the European Commission as being of particular practical importance: gender equality, public engagement, open access, science education, and ethics. The overarching theme that emerges from the analysis is that while RRI opportunities and challenges are fairly easy to manage in a low-digitalization scenario, digital transformation greatly increases the number and complexity of the RRI opportunities and challenges with which regional R&I actors must contend.

1. INTRODUCTION

The project DigiTeRRI elaborates a framework and develops a roadmap for a responsible transition of traditional industry regions into digitalized industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by using a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach. The co-creation of the framework, the roadmapping process, and the implementation of actions will take place with partners and their stakeholders from three territories in Europe, Värmland in Sweden, Région Grand Est in France, and Styria in Austria. To facilitate the co-creation process, it is important to understand the DigiTeRRI common framework as this will allow different territories to use the same methodology (roadmapping) to incorporate RRI into their digitalization efforts. This is the main objective of the present report - deliverable D3.2.

The common framework is built on the background knowledge of transition processes (multi-level perspective), regional innovation policy (Smart Specialisation), digitalization (current societal and industrial trends), and responsible research and innovation (process dimensions). Our main argument is that the transition process of a traditional industry region to a digitalized R&I ecosystem can be supported by a responsible roadmapping process. The RRI approach is incorporated in the four steps of the roadmapping process (stocktaking, visioning, roadmap development, and roadmap implementation), as well as the destination of transition itself (digitalized R&I ecosystem). This common framework will serve as a shared knowledge base and vocabulary for DigiTeRRI partners to use within the project.

The structure of the rest of this report is as follows. Section 2 introduces the background context and explains key concepts. Section 3 presents the common framework, consisting of the roadmapping methodology and an overview of how digital maturity affects the opportunities and challenges for practicing RRI. Section 4 summarizes the main findings and discusses how this deliverable will be used in the DigiTeRRI project going forward.

2. BACKGROUND CONTEXT

This section sets the stage for developing the DigiTeRRI conceptual framework by briefly introducing the context of the project, regional transition. It also addresses the main concepts on which DigiTeRRI is based: transition process, digitalization, responsible research and innovation (RRI), self-sustaining research and innovation (R&I) ecosystems, and regional development strategies.

2.1 Transition process: Multi-level perspective (MLP)

The DigiTeRRI project concentrates on territories which are currently undergoing the change from the traditional industrial production, e.g. forge, foundry, plastics processing, subcontracting of automotive parts, machine tools, chemistry, food processing, paper production, etc., to a digitalized industry region which brings many new opportunities. However, experts also raise concerns that organizations might be unable to adapt to this revolution flooding our lives and societal, cultural, economic system, and the industries.

Territories with traditional industries are familiar with a situation in which the businesses of the region operate in a fast changing and unstable environment nowadays. Such territories can only survive if they learn how to adapt to the changes in their industries and stay competitive by adding new value to products and services, taking into account the societal and environmental challenges. Many of these territories were shaped by their historical orientation to heavy industry. Most of them have been struggling since the 1980s with changing their regional orientation, for developing a sustainable economic system by specialisation in new technology fields using digitalisation.

Regional transition to digitalisation combines multiple perspectives in different ways and encompasses multiple levels. The multilevel perspective (Geels, 2002, 2004) may be seen as inspired by theories of structuration. Structuration theory (Giddens, 1984; Jessop, 2001) combines a view of how economic structures and institutionalised regimes of inter-locking rules maintain path continuity. The relation between structure and action consists of rules and institutional complementarities which selects actions which support the trajectory and tend to exclude others. At the same time, structures may open up for and allow a dynamic which starts with micro level actors (entrepreneurs, niches, innovators) who decide to move outside the limitations of the structural path of development. In this way, the structural and institutional macro level context is likely to work as a selection mechanism, a filter, which accepts certain new niches/ opportunities of growth, and rejects others. This process of transition (Geels, 2018) as illustrated in **Figure 1**, involves: (a) micro level, i.e. transformative innovations, seen as entrepreneurial discoveries or emerging needs (Niches), (b) meso level, i.e. system's sets of rules and practices in which successful niches or discoveries start to grow and multiply (Patchwork of regimes), and (c) macro-level, i.e. regional sets of factors, including technical, societal, political, economic, megatrends, etc., which influence regimes but over which regime actors have little or no influence in the short run (Landscape). This process of transformation takes place within the context of a territory or region, which includes material infrastructures, public sector institutions, institutions of research and learning, as well as labour markets. Among sociologists studying paradigms, the regional level is referred to as “landscapes”. Landscapes are material and spatial arrangements of cities, factories, highways, and energy infrastructures (Geels, 2004).

Source: Adapted from Geels (2002).

Figure 1: Multi-level framework for analysing socio-technical transitions.

Technological transformations involve a complex interplay between humans, their organizations and networks, and technological artefacts, such as machines, robots, transportation, and communication infrastructures and so on. A recent study of man-machine relations following digitalisation (Frey & Osborne, 2017) focuses on characteristics of work which may be taken by machines, seen in relation to work descriptions of professions existing in the US labour market today. Frey and Osborne (2017) calculated that whereas most functions which today are regarded as occupational employment in production had a large probability of being digitalized, whereas positions in management, including supervision in factories, as well as science, engineering and education, were likely to be performed by humans. Tentatively, it seems as if we might be talking about densely organized human teams which are able to understand and match the complexities of the machine hardware and software operations. This assumption corresponds to a recent literature survey on studies of digital transformations of socio-technical systems (Bockshecker et al., 2018) where collaboration, knowledge sharing, communication and connectivity are key issues.

It is important to keep in mind that the success of multi-level approach does not only happen by processes within the technological niche, but also requires the support at the existing regimes and the sociotechnical landscape of the regions (Geels, 2002). The alignment of the developments at three levels, which are interrelated but also have their own internal dynamics, determines if the transformation will be successful or not. The transition

involves not only technology and market shares but also changes on wider dimensions such as regulation and policy, infrastructure, industrial networks, organizations, and mindset. The aim of the DigiTeRRI project is to create a common framework for transitioning traditional industry regions to digitalized R&I ecosystem which brings together knowledge and understandings at three levels (illustrated by **Figure 2**):

- Macro level: Understanding digitalization key trends and their relations to RRI (sections 2.4 and 2.5).
- Meso level: Understanding about the regional innovation policy and strategy related to digitalization (section 2.2) as well as the roadmapping process for transitioning (section 3.1).
- Micro level: Understanding about innovation actors in the R&I ecosystems (section 2.3), their challenges and opportunities when implementing RRI-oriented digitalization practices (section 3.2).

Source: adapted from Geels (2002).

Figure 2: DigiTeRRI and the dynamics of MLP on digitalization.

2.2 Regional innovation policy: Smart Specialisation Strategy

The common element of regional policy in the three DigiTeRRI regions is that their regional economic development is linked to Smart Specialisation Strategy. Smart Specialisation, conceived within the Cohesion policy of the European Commission, is an approach to boost growth and jobs in Europe by bringing together relevant actors in the regions to identify and develop their own regional competitive advantages (European Commission, 2020c, 2020b). Each region that employs Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) will set their priorities for investment based on an inclusive process of stakeholder engagement, including local authorities, academia, business and industry, and the civil society.

All three territories in DigiTeRRI are employing S3 as a regional strategy (for more details, please refer to D2.3). Therefore, knowing how digitalization is prioritized in each region's S3 will give us a better understanding of the alignment between digitalization trends (macro-level) and regional socio-technical regimes (meso-level) and the digitalized activities from R&I actors (micro-level). The sub-sections below briefly summarize the role of S3 in each of the three territories. This information serves as background knowledge on how government policy currently drives digitalization in the territories. Since the regional governments are committed to these policies, the policies affect the possibility space for creating feasible, realistic roadmaps. This knowledge is therefore important for the roadmapping process in DigiTeRRI.

2.2.1 *Smart specialisation and its role in regional economic development in Värmland*

Region Värmland was very early involved in the EU's smart specialisation policy processes and has been in the forefront in Sweden when it comes to influencing Swedish national policy on smart specialisation as well as very active within the S3 and RIS3 networks. As with the Värmland Strategy, the Värmland's Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation 2015-2020 was co-created with triple helix stakeholders in a process during 2014-2015. What has made Värmland unique in its S3 is that it has specifically included the gender dimension in all its priorities. This proactive decision is based upon the understanding that gender mixed groups are more innovative and in order to stimulate the transformation of the labour market within Värmland it needs to be attractive to both women and men, the reasoning for this is that the dominating export industries have traditionally been dominated by men with male values and male codes.

Currently (December 2020) Region Värmland is, as the regional authority responsible for regional development in the territory, leading two concurrent co-creation processes. One process focuses upon the Värmland Strategy 2040 which encompasses a broader regional economic development perspective, the second process focuses

upon the Värmland Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Sustainable Specialisation 2021-2027. Both these strategies are due to be implemented during 2021.

Värmland's current smart specialisation strategy consists of one horizontal priority and five more specific priorities for the region in relation to smart specialisation. The horizontal priority is Value-creating Services, and the five priorities which have in turn been prioritised and are thus ranked in the following order: 1) forest-based economy; 2) digitalisation of welfare services; 3) advanced manufacturing and complex systems; 4) nature, culture and place based digitalized experiences; and 5) system solutions with photovoltaics. The rationale behind these priorities is that smart specialisation in Värmland is both about what Värmland is good at as well as good for. OECD stated, in their evaluation of the Academy for Smart Specialisation (2020), that smart specialisation has been a transformational force in Värmland by promoting new specialisations and skills in a variety of sectors, such as the forest-based bioeconomy, ICT and care, smart industry and tourism, among others. The region so far has managed to capitalise on existing strengths as well as generate new knowledge networks. This by bringing clear priorities into the regional agenda has facilitated the allocation of available resources, and digitalization has played an important role in these S3 priorities of Värmland.

The R&I actors within Värmland are active on several political arenas, and one of these arenas at the national level in Sweden is Reglab. Using Reglab's innovation index we can see that Värmland has moved from being in 15th to 11th place in the ranking of regions within Sweden during the period 2015-2019. Part of the explanations are structural reasons that require a longer time perspective to have a visible impact and this is echoed by an independent expert evaluation carried out on behalf of Swedish Agency for Economic and Regional Growth. In this evaluation, three sets of challenges were identified: 1) structural in relation to regional size and critical mass, and the role that regional authorities have; 2) institutional in relation to the lack of mandate and/or mission within the policy area, and when it comes to ERDF implementation processes; and 3) operational when it comes to the innovation support system, and research links that the regions experience. Paulsson's findings on challenges thus support some of the structural challenges identified by Region Värmland evaluations on the Värmland Strategy's goal that focuses upon innovation. The Academy for Smart Specialisation is a continual collaboration between Region Värmland and University of Karlstad, during 2010-2014 there was an agreement of intention of which 10 new professorships was established at Karlstad University with focus on the areas prioritised for regional development, the continuation included research within these prioritised areas. There is close collaboration between actors in order to increase the economic competitiveness of the region for example between Region Värmland, Karlstad University, and the cluster organisations representing regional industry for example the Paper Province, Compare, and Visit Värmland.

2.2.2 Smart specialisation and its role in regional economic development in Styria

Styria has joined the Smart Specialisation Platform in 2016. Styria's economic strategy ("Growth through Innovation") employs S3 to enable economic growth, expand employment opportunities and foster competitiveness through innovation. The S3 priorities in Styria are: (1) Mobility; (2) Green Technology; (3) Health and Food technology. Digital transformation has been the policy objectives for S3 priorities (European Commission, 2020a).

2.2.3 Smart specialisation and its role in regional economic development in Grand-Est

For more than 10 years, the European Commission (DG REGIO) asked the Regions to focus a part of the European Regional Development Fund on innovation through a Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) (axis one of the Operational Plan /ERDF).

For the next period 2021-2027, the Region Grand Est will define a new S3, that will cover the whole region. In 2014, the Region Grand Est does not exist and three different S3 were designed and implemented in Alsace, Lorraine et Champagne-Ardenne.

The smart specialization strategy (S3) extends the regional economic development, higher education and innovation strategies developed by the Grand Est Region. It aims to identify a small number of highly competitive areas that already exist or are emerging, which allow them to differentiate themselves from other European regions. S3 is a necessary reference framework to act as a lever with European funds. As such, it guides the financing of innovation projects which will be supported by the ERDF. It is in this context that the Region approved at the end of 2020, the priorities of the S3 du Grand Est for the period 2021-2027, in order to be able to integrate it into the draft ERDF Operational Program which will be submitted to the European Commission mid-2021.

The priorities selected for the S3 du Grand Est concern 8 sectors of activity: technologies and equipment for industrial transition, recycling, and functionalization of materials for industry and for construction, medical biotechnologies, digital tools for health, medical devices, biobased molecules and materials, tools and systems for the sustainable and intelligent management of natural resources, energy systems and their performance. In addition, there are five transversal priorities: digital transformation (including the deployment of use cases of artificial intelligence), social innovation, responsible innovation, short circuits and relocation. These priorities are thus intended to make the Grand Est region an even more competitive, aggressive and at the forefront of innovation, with one objective: to be the major region of reference in the heart of Europe.

2.3 Self-sustaining R&I Ecosystems

In DigiTeRRI, we view R&I ecosystems similarly with innovation ecosystems and innovation system. An innovation system consists of actors who are doing innovation activities and the interaction of these actors. The entirety of private and public organisations and individuals, which contribute by their activities and interactions to the creation and diffusion of new technologies, new products or new knowledge, build an innovation system (see Fischer & Fröhlich, 2001). For instance, Freeman describes an innovation system by “... the network of institutions in the public and private sectors whose activities and interactions initiate, import, modify, and diffuse new technologies.” (Freeman, 1987, p. 1).

The study of innovation systems started more than thirty years back. Innovation systems approaches can focus on national level as Lundvall (2010), or Nelson (1993), or Edquist (2012) worked out. The innovation system on the regional level was for instance described by Braczyk et al. (2004). The sectoral innovation system was characterised by Malerba (2004), or Malerba (2005), or Dolata (2009). Carlsson and Stankiewicz (1991), or Johnson and Jacobsson (2001), or Hekkert et al. (2007) studies the technological innovation systems.

The collaboration in innovation systems is crucial. The conditions for co-operation between industry and research, between big leading companies and SMEs are an important foundation for an appropriate innovation “climate”. In addition, the legal frame and the support from policy makers accelerates the innovation success.

DigiTeRRI goes one step further. How does innovation impact on society and especially digitalisation and that in specific territories? DigiTeRRI develops a framework and elaborates a roadmap for the transition of traditional regions into digitalized territory by responsible research and innovation (RRI). Therefore, civil society is also engaged into the DigiTeRRI innovation system. The actors in such an innovation ecosystem can be categorised with the four types of the Quadruple Helix (“4H”), namely by industry & business, science & research, citizens & civil society, and by government & policy. The interlinkages and collaborations within these actors of the innovation ecosystem generate and create innovation, products, economic success, governmental conditions for living and doing business.

The way of interactions between these actor types (**Figure 3**) and their linkages to other territories and the whole world (e.g. specific universities, or high-tech SMEs and large companies in other parts in the world) combined with a high living standard and wellbeing for the society in the territory is an important basis for a healthy innovation ecosystem.

Source: Own representation (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology).

Figure 3: The actors in an innovation ecosystem.

Innovation ecosystems will be explained in detail in section 2.3.2, but an introduction is in order to appreciate the next section. In short, innovation ecosystems are another approach in the area of innovation systems referring to the complex relationships that are formed between actors or entities whose functional goal is to enable technology development, research and innovation (Jackson, 2011; Oh et al., 2016). Innovation ecosystem research recognizes that territories, defined as any particular area characterised by certain geographical features, or any area with shared cultural, environmental or economic ties, are “highly complex living systems” (Magnaghi, 2005, p. 62) which consist of variable contextual interrelationships, processes, interactions and dynamics related to society, geography, economy and environment. With this in mind, we can proceed to discussing shifts from traditional industry territories to digitalized industry territories.

2.3.1 From traditional industry territories to digitalized industry territories

Within low-tech industries the gap between those who stick to their traditional businesses and others who are adopting digitally transformed businesses is becoming larger every day. Today, intelligent and suitable forms of digitalisation are relevant for the survival of any business sector, especially for traditional ones. Therefore, this transition process should be well defined and reflected to make sure the change process will be successful for the distinct companies and the entire region.

Digitalized industry territories are territories with a high level of digitalisation in their industrial sectors, i.e. a high level of digital development and usage of ICT innovations, taking into account social as well as technical elements.

The process of transitioning one traditional territory to become a digitalized territory is called digital transformation. In this report, we use digitization when referring to the technological transformation of “analog information into digital format”; we use digitalisation to describe the current state of digital development; and we use digital transformation to refer to the process of organizational and societal changes driven by innovations and developments of ICT, including the ability to adopt technologies rapidly which affects social as well as technical elements of business models, processes, products and the organizational structure.

Paradigm shifts within industries require a new socio-technical system to be created, with a different supporting infrastructure. Niches shaping new technological paradigms may be expected to move through certain stages. There is an installation period where the basic core of the paradigm, or gestation is formed.

These factors constitute a sequence of S-curves or waves, with the historical industrialization as the First Deep Transition (Schot & Kanger, 2018). Today, it is speculated that we might face the start of the Second-Deep Transition, which breaks with the cumulative logic of the last 250 years of industrial revolution, with digitalisation as its driving mechanism.

With these industry transitions in mind, we now turn to innovation ecosystems, their constituent parts, and what makes them successful.

2.3.2 The Digitalized Innovation Ecosystem

In recent years, ecosystem research has exploded in popularity in response to empirical evidence on the interdependencies between organizations and the necessity to cooperate in order to create value (Bogers et al., 2019). For example, the ecosystem stream of research has provided evidence that ecosystems were necessary

to develop computers from mainframes to desktop computers and finally to smartphones. This development was only made possible by building complex cooperative networks of hardware and software suppliers (Bresnahan & Greenstein, 1999; Gawer & Cusumano, 2002; West & Mace, 2010). Similar complexities are common in modern retail infrastructure, where supply and distribution networks are structured to provide redundancy and efficiency as to maximize availability and minimize costs (Iansiti & Levien, 2004). There is also a strong regional component to ecosystems in some contexts, especially those where regional entrepreneurial clusters are located (Finegold, 1999). However, as we will discover below, increase digitalization can somewhat offset these effects. Regardless, as we can see, there is ample evidence for the importance of ecosystems.

While ecosystems are undoubtedly important, research on ecosystems is fragmented and suffers from a multitude of sometimes incompatible definitions. In a recent literature review, Bogers et al. (2019) identifies 4 different streams of ecosystem research: *value networks*, *platforms*, *two (or more) sided markets*, and *entrepreneurial ecosystems*. It is important to note that these streams can all study an ecosystem *context* such as an *innovation* ecosystem but would take different perspectives or examine different parts of the empirical whole (Bogers et al., 2019). While these different perspectives have made it difficult to create a general definition of all ecosystems, there seems to be a wide agreement that the main purpose of an ecosystem is “*to create value that no single firm could have created alone*” (Adner, 2006, p. 100 [print version]). This also extends to the context of innovation ecosystems.

With this description in mind, it is useful to ask the question: *what the particulars of innovation ecosystems are?* as to set them apart from other ecosystem types. Rinkinen (2016, p. 27) argues that “[t]he innovation ecosystem can be viewed as a wider concept than the business ecosystem concept as it also includes the political, economic and technological environment affecting the ecosystem and its members.” The business ecosystem concept would be business organizations working together to create value. We agree with this statement, but would add that in the DigiTeRRI project, we take a 4H approach, and therefore include society in our understanding of the innovation ecosystem.

Having created a common understanding of what innovation ecosystems are in the DigiTeRRI project, we must still answer one more question before proceeding to the next section: *what is a digitalized innovation ecosystem?* As might be expected due to the bleeding-edge nature of the concept, there appears to be no common understanding of what constitutes a digitalized innovation ecosystem. However, in a working paper, Jensen et al. (2021), argues that a digitalized innovation ecosystem must necessarily 1) consist of 4H actors, all of which must have 2) the competency to utilize infrastructure for digitalization, and 3) must engage in behaviours which will create value that no single firm could create alone. The willingness to engage in these behaviours are contingent on incentives for the different 4H actors, e.g., knowledge creation for academics, profit

motives for businesses, policy implementation for policy makers, and protecting interest groups interests for CSOs (Jensen et al. working paper). A successful innovation ecosystem manages to balance the willingness and incentives for all 4H actors, thereby ensuring their participation and, value creation beyond what a single organization could create alone (Jensen et al., 2021).

This value creation can arrive from several sources (Jensen et al., 2021). Here we highlight two which are particularly salient in the DigiTeRRI network: efficiency gains and network valence. The efficiency gains from transitioning from an innovation system to a digitalized innovation system seem obvious (albeit very much context dependent): reductions in transaction costs (both in terms of lower communication costs but also due to information clarity), opportunities for automation, use of shared data through common APIs, training of AI through pooled data, and so on. Network valence can be increased by as local communication becomes more efficient and effective, i.e., achieving cluster like effects ecosystem effects as described by Finegold (1999), but also through connecting with other innovation ecosystems beyond regions. This separates innovation ecosystems from digitalized innovation systems as the latter is better enabled to transfer knowledge between innovation systems separated by geographical distance. In sum, digitalized innovation ecosystems are substantially different from innovation ecosystems.

With this in mind, we transition into recent digitalization trends. These trends correlate directly with different 4H actors, their competency in utilizing digitalization infrastructure, and their behaviours.

2.4 Digitalization: Current societal and industrial trends

The overall aim of this section is to critically assess current trends in digitalization and thereby provide background knowledge for our analysis of how digitalization affects the challenges and opportunities for practicing RRI (section 3.2). To understand the real-world implications of digitalization for RRI, it's important to first have an awareness of real-world trends and developments in digitalization. This section can also serve as the background knowledge for the stakeholders who participate in the roadmapping workshops in WP4 to understand the overall digitalization context.

In this report, digitalization can be understood in the broad sense as applications of digital technologies, either at regional strategy or business sector. When reviewing the literature, we uncovered several future trends that appear to be particularly important in this regard. Since academic research in the social sciences often study what has already transpired, this section draws heavily on studies and reports from the EU, the OECD, and other organizations that have recently reviewed what they perceive as digitalization trends based on primary data collection, secondary data sources, expert opinions, and forecasting models. Their findings are nuanced by

analysis of academic research where relevant. Relying on findings from such reports are subject to one limitation: the trend analysis by the EU, the OECD, and others, do not take a RRI perspective per se. However, many of the digitalization issues of concern to these parties are very much interpretable under an RRI lens. Our interpretations are presented below.

COVID-19

The issue of digitalization in emergency situations has grown in importance in light of the recent COVID-19 epidemic. For example, internet connectivity has proven invaluable for practicing social distancing while maintaining work productivity. Demands for broadband communication services skyrocketed during the start of the outbreak, reflected in a new record in bandwidth use within the G20 countries, breaking the previous record with 47%. In Europe, those countries that were affected the worst by the epidemic displayed the biggest growth in bandwidth. For example, Italy increased its bandwidth usage by 40% compared to an 1.8% increase the previous year. France's growth rate was multiplied by 2.4¹.

While internet connectivity has proven to be incredibly important during this crisis, the use of IoT devices, apps for smart phones, and similar have raised important privacy concerns. One group of observers (Newlands et al., 2020) has already drawn attention to this issue as they examined how some countries, for example Norway, rushed to deploy an infection tracking mobile application that was later temporarily halted by Norway's privacy watch dog (Datatilsynet, 2020a, 2020b). Some academics argue that the immediate pressing issue of COVID-19 should allow us to break with prior standards and approval processes (Harris et al., 2020), while others urge caution pointing out immediate dangers of rushed innovations (Callaway, 2020) and others about the long-term consequences (Harari, 2020; Toh & Brown, 2020). The trade-offs of such rushed innovations and their ethical and societal impacts will likely be debated in the months and years to come.

Turning now to the discussion on use of technologies not strictly related to COVID-19, we find multiple privacy issues in technologies used to maintain social distancing and work productivity. For example, Zoom, a popular videoconferencing tool that has experienced tremendous user growth since the start of the pandemic has been fraught with security and privacy issues (Hodge, 2020). Beyond issues of privacy, internet trolls quickly realized that Zoom conferences without any login restrictions could be used as an outlet for anti-Semitism and racism (Hodge, 2020). While both issues are supposedly solved at this time, these examples illustrate the difficulty of moderating modern digital platforms.

¹ Surprisingly, the UK's bandwidth growth rates remained stable.

It is necessary here to clarify that the dependence on such technologies mentioned above has other important implications. In a recent literature review of COVID-19's impact on gender equality, Carli (2020) identified three significant impacts on gender equality. These are: (1) more women have lost their jobs than men; (2) women are more likely to hold jobs that expose them to infection, and (3) women have experienced more work disruption than men due to increases in childcare and other responsibilities. Carli (2020) does, however, point out that there may be a silver lining to this story: as men telecommute more, they take a more active role in childcare which might increase their long-term participation in raising their children.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In the new global economy, Artificial Intelligence has become a central topic in many industries. In the literature on responsibility and ethics, the importance of artificial intelligence has been subject to considerable discussion. There are several reasons why this discussion has become so dominant. On the one, there are great opportunities in AI. Analysis of food scarcity patterns can supposedly help combat hunger, medical diagnosis can be made more effective and less error-prone, hitherto hidden patterns of discrimination can be uncovered, and more.

Along with this growth in AI, however, there is increasing concern over violations of human rights—accidentally or deliberately (OECD, 2019a, 2019b, 2020). Accidental violations could stem from algorithm bias, poor quality data, faulty designs, or complex interactions between the AI system and its environment. One particularly timely example of algorithm bias would be the rise of social media echo-chambers and fake news because of algorithms aligning displayed content with what the user finds agreeable and is willing to share with their peers (Boulianne et al., 2020; Cardenal et al., 2019; Engesser et al., 2017). While there is some disagreement between academics on the topic, recent unfortunate events in USA have made it abundantly clear that social media is considered by many outside of academia to share some of the blame of said events. As illustrated above, there are several ways in which AI can incidentally lead to negative outcomes. On the other hand, there are plenty of examples of how AI can deliberately be used to similar effects, for example tracking of political dissidents, restriction freedom of expression, or hindering participation in political life. Considering all of this evidence, it seems that AI has the potential to violate human rights.

Another issue that is not exclusive to AI, but decidedly amplified by it, is that of deanonymization of anonymized data. As early as 2007, two graduate students at the University of Texas at Austin were able to deanonymize supposedly anonymous datasets from Netflix and movie ratings from IMDB, a website where users can rate movies (Narayanan & Shmatikov, 2008). A simple search on a prominent academic publication paper indexer service shows that there have been thousands of papers on various forms of deanonymization techniques in the

last 3 years, many of them driven by AI techniques. This represents a clear privacy issue, and a trend that will become increasingly important.

ROBOTIZATION

Another important trend in digitalization that has RRI implications is increase in robotization and automation. Over the past decade, automation research in the social sciences has emphasized the consequences of robotization on employment. In 2013 Frey and Osborne (Frey & Osborne, 2017, the 2013 edition was a working paper and policy document) shocked analysts and policy makers by suggesting that 47% of American jobs are in danger of going away due to automation. Since then, several other researchers and institutions have also estimated robotization related job loss numbers in the high double digits (Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018). In their interesting analysis, Nedelkoska and Quintini (2018) find that countries with strong economies will be left somewhat unscathed by automation; weaker economies, however, are likely to fare far worse. As an example, they show that 33% of all jobs in Slovakia can be automated, while this is the case for only 6% of jobs in Norway. But even for highly developed economies, there is a particularly vulnerable group within them: young people. Perhaps surprising, as young people are often thought of as more skilled at digitalization than earlier generations, they are also more likely to only find employment in entry level jobs. These jobs are in turn more susceptible to automation (Nedelkoska & Quintini, 2018).

Two important themes emerge from the automation studies discussed so far: all economies--but particularly the weaker ones--and young people everywhere are particularly vulnerable to automation. A key policy priority should therefore be to plan for the long-term implications of automation, and especially for particularly vulnerable regions and groups.

DIGITALIZATION AND SCIENCE EDUCATION

In the literature on science education within the education system, the relative importance of digitalization has been subject to considerable discussion. One of the most important events of the 1980s was the advent of the personal computer. A major advantage of the personal computer is that it allows for running education software. The first serious discussions and analyses of digitalization and science education emerged during the mid-1980s with Marks (1982)'s study demonstrating the effectiveness of visualization of complex content visualization. Other early examples of science education and digitalization research include self-paced video learning (Leonard, 1985), teaching through tools designed to model authentic phenomena (Doerr, 1996), and simulation of real-life environments (Westera et al., 1997). However, it is only since the emergence of the internet that the study of science education and digitalization has gained momentum (Neumann & Waight, 2020). Since then, studies have emerged on e-learning for independent learning (Ajadi et al., 2007), and intelligent systems for

intelligently monitoring and supporting students (Graesser et al., 2011). More recently, literature has emerged that offers contradictory findings about the effectiveness of digitalization in science education (Krajcik & Mun, 2014). Neumann and Waigth (2020) in introducing their special issue, argues that previously published studies on the effect of digitalization on science education are not consistent because the question of *under which conditions do digitalization improve science education?* has been ignored. In other words, more research, and careful deliberation of practitioners on this topic needs to be undertaken before the association between digitalization and science education is more clearly understood.

Together the studies presented in this section provide important background knowledge for understanding how trends in digitalization may have consequences for RRI. Section 3.2 will address in a more systematic manner the question of how digitalization affects the opportunities and challenges for practicing RRI.

2.5 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Responsible research and innovation (RRI) refers, in a broad sense, to research and innovation activities that are aligned with the values and needs of society. The concept has been evolving along two parallel tracks, one political and one academic (Burget et al., 2017). Politically, the European Commission has been the driving force in an ongoing quest to define RRI and promote the practical implementation of the concept in Europe. Inspired by – and in turn inspiring – this movement, academics have turned various theoretical lenses to the notion of responsibility in innovation, seeking to clarify its meaning and potential implications. Scholars tend to use the terms “responsible innovation” (RI) and “responsible research and innovation” (RRI) interchangeably (Schomberg, 2013). There is considerable overlap between the concept of RRI as championed by the European Commission and the concepts of RI and RRI as used in academia. However, while the EU has been emphasizing concrete policy agendas such as gender equality, academic research has tended to focus on more abstract dimensions and conceptualizations of RRI.

The justification for coining a special responsibility concept for innovation, distinct from more general notions of responsibility, lies in the observation that technological innovations are becoming ever more powerful and the scope of their impact ever less predictable. Research and innovation cannot be governed solely by rules because rules are formed in response to the past, not the future (Owen et al., 2012). Responsibility in innovation requires governance mechanisms beyond simple regulation. The literature on RRI explores what these mechanisms might be.

In one of the most common conceptualization of RRI in the academic literature, responsible conduct in research and innovation is broken down into four process dimensions: anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, and

responsiveness (Stilgoe et al., 2013). *Anticipation* refers to the systematic consideration of possible future harmful consequences of research and innovation activities. *Reflexivity* denotes the practice of continuously scrutinizing one's own activities, assumptions, commitments, knowledge, and values in order to equip oneself to make more responsible decisions. *Inclusion* means being open to the views of external stakeholders, including the general public, when making decisions related to the future direction of research and innovation. *Responsiveness* involves taking action to adjust the trajectory of research and innovation activities in response to new knowledge, perspectives, and norms (Hansen et al., 2020).

In this project we adopt a slightly modified (and perhaps slightly more intuitive) version of the framework described above, developed in the EU project RRI Tools.² In this version of the framework, the four dimensions are: diversity and inclusion; anticipation and reflexivity; openness and transparency; and responsiveness and adaptivity. More information on this breakdown of RRI process dimensions can be found in section 3.1.3.

In the political arena, the European Commission has been championing the concept of RRI for years, but the components of the official EU “package” of RRI policy agendas has been adjusted over time and is likely to continue to evolve in the future. Indeed, DigiTeRRI is one of a number of EU projects that embody the ambition of the EU to refine the concept of RRI and find ways of implementing it in practice. As of this writing, the European Commission defines 5 thematic elements of RRI as being particularly urgent for aligning R&I with the interests of society; these five “RRI keys” are public engagement, open access, gender, ethics, and science education.³

The DigiTeRRI project takes the perspective that the RRI process dimensions from the academic literature and the 5 RRI keys from the European Commission are complementary, and therefore takes both into consideration in the course of the project.

RRI processes provide suitable procedures to address the transformation challenge within traditional industries, in particular because of the reflexive nature of the implemented innovation process. Early involvement of stakeholder groups, users and citizens as well as the development of additional or alternative knowledge sources provide a broader, more plural and thus more legitimate basis for decision-making. Indicators for measuring RRI were identified and defined within the so-called MoRRI project – “Monitoring the evolution and benefits of Responsible Research and Innovation” (Publications Office of the European Union, 2019) - such as gender equality, public engagement, science literacy and science education, ethics and open access.

² <https://rri-tools.eu/>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

With this background context in mind, the DigiTeRRI project aims to develop a framework and actions to transition the traditional industry regions into digitalized industrial regions with self-sustaining, responsible R&I ecosystems. The three regions involved are Värmland in Sweden, Région Grand Est in France, and Styria in Austria.

2.5.1 RRI approach

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) emphasizes that research and innovation must be aligned with societal values and needs. The policy agenda for RRI therefore focuses on both mitigating the negative effects of research and innovation in areas with potentially adverse societal effects, as well as actively supporting research in areas where the societal benefit is high, for instance in addressing grand societal challenges. RRI envisages that responsible researchers and innovators actively construct their ‘responsibility’, reflecting the need for researchers to communicate and discuss their results to build social support for and permit social guidance of their research efforts (Owen et al., 2012).

Underlying the RRI policy is a fear that society has lost control over science and innovation despite the increasing sums of direct and indirect public funding that stimulate and facilitate research and innovation. Research policy has become increasingly oriented towards scientific excellence, and innovation policy increasingly oriented towards competitiveness. In this process, there is a risk that the social value of research and innovation is lost, or at least is increasingly up to researchers and innovators themselves to preserve. RRI proponents contend that these policy arrangements create governance frameworks which are insufficient to control the development of research and new technology in potentially ethically problematic areas, such as genetics, biosciences and information technology. In these fields, the pursuit of new knowledge creates opportunities to develop new technologies, but technology should not be created for its own sake. Societal voices must also influence discussions concerning which knowledge will be developed in which directions for which purposes.

2.5.2 Responsible R&I ecosystem: the combination of RRI and digital transformation

Digitalisation causes a complete paradigm shift of production and innovation options. RRI may deliver relevant aspects to support and guide the digital transition in an adequate way, in order to make sure that outcomes of the process will make sense for all stakeholders which means regarding not only economic values but also strongly and early addressing social and ecological challenges taking into account certain ethical principles and normative aims.

In the course of addressing the issue of digitalisation, the RRI principles can be addressed as well, thus providing a comprehensive implementation of RRI. In the transition of old classical to new digitalized production, many unanswered and challenging questions will pop up. The development of a future strategy must involve both government and society, as well as science, research and businesses. The transition in technology opens new gates in the interaction of society and science and will offer an excellent environment for introducing and implementing RRI. Since the overall innovation system is undergoing a significant change, the need for new solutions and thus the opportunity for implementing RRI actions is remarkably high. Self-organisation phenomena of complex systems reveal that constraints imposed from outside a system appear to be drivers for change.

3. COMMON FRAMEWORK

The basic premise of DigiTeRRI is that the traditional industry regions that are represented in the project will undergo a transition process in which they will raise their general level of digital maturity. The destination that the regions aspire to reach is a digitalized, responsible R&I ecosystem. The method that will be used for guiding this transition is roadmapping. RRI plays a role in the transition at two levels. First, RRI must be integrated into the roadmapping process that guides the transition process (RRI + roadmapping = “RRI-oriented roadmapping”). Second, RRI must be integrated into the transition destination (RRI + digitalization = “RRI-oriented digitalization”). The common framework we will present in this section addresses both levels. The common framework synthesizes relevant literature as well as findings from previous DigiTeRRI deliverables to ensure synergy and coherence within the project. **Figure 4** below illustrates the framework, showing the four steps of the roadmapping process (to be elaborated in section 3.2) and indicating the two different ways in which RRI will be taken into consideration.

In designing the co-creation process for the roadmaps, DigiTeRRI gives priority to making sure that the co-creation process is aligned with the four RRI principles of inclusivity, anticipation, transparency, and responsiveness. On the other hand, it would be impractical for the stakeholders involved in the roadmapping process to apply such abstract RRI principles when attempting to define the role of RRI in the digital transition process of their region. Therefore, when working with stakeholders on this task, we switch our focus to the five specific RRI “keys” defined by the European Commission: gender equality, public engagement, open access, science education, and ethics.

Section 3.1 below explains the roadmapping process, while section 3.2 addresses the question of how to take RRI into account in digitalization.

Figure 4: DigiTeRRI common framework. Source: Own presentation (NRI)

3.1 Roadmapping process: embedded with RRI dimensions

DigiTeRRI emphasizes the implementation of action plans for transitioning the chosen territories to digitalized resilient responsible research and innovation ecosystems. We apply roadmapping methodology for all three territories in the transitioning process.

3.1.1 What is a roadmap and what is roadmapping?

When we consider a roadmap from a general point of view, we can say that a roadmap is an itinerary of paths or routes that leads to some geographical space. A roadmap serves as a tool for travellers, which provides essential understanding, proximity, direction, and some degree of certainty in travel planning. A roadmap guides the driver of the vehicle to the destination.

In management literature, a roadmap is a metaphor for strategic planning. Roadmapping is a bridge between strategic and operational innovation management. Roadmapping describes the process of roadmap

development. The earliest approaches to roadmapping date to the 1980s. Since then, roadmapping has become a standard methodology of future-oriented research.

The creation of roadmaps has its roots in technology-intensive companies. Due to the increasing complexity of products and processes, these companies faced the problem of how to keep track of important technologies. There was a shortage of explicit, framework-structured representations of future developments in products and production processes for many organisations. Roadmapping offers an approach to address this challenge. The following terms play an important role in a roadmap process (International Energy Agency, 2014, p. 4):

Roadmap is a specific type of strategic plan. It outlines activities of an organisation which have to be undertaken over specified time frames to achieve stated goals and outcomes.

Roadmapping is the evolving process. This process creates a roadmap, implements and monitors actions, and updates the roadmap if necessary.

Setting a vision is necessary for developing a roadmap. The vision gives the direction for the roadmap. It is a motivating, positively formulated representation of a desired future state. The vision expresses where you want to be and what you want to stand for in the future.

Stakeholders are affected by the actions, and therefore they co-create the roadmap together. They have an interest in the roadmap, support it, and have the power to implement the developed goals and measures.

Implementation of the measures is the process of putting a roadmap into action, by carrying out projects and initiatives that address roadmap tasks and priorities, and by monitoring progress using a tracking system.

There are different types of roadmaps (Camarinha-Matos & Afsarmanesh, 2004):

Technology roadmaps represent technology trends and their dependencies on possible disruptive business ideas. They show investment potential and derive further measures from technology developments to products.

Product roadmaps link potential markets with technologies and predict the chances of success of the products described.

A **market roadmap** represents potential future markets for existing and new business models, products, and services.

Company roadmaps: The individual roadmaps of the various business areas in the company are aggregated into a company-wide roadmap. Synergies and gaps in the innovation portfolio are identified in order to develop corrective measures.

There are also *science roadmaps* and *innovation roadmaps*, not further discussed here.

The literature describes mainly methodologies for technology roadmaps for companies, not roadmaps for territories or regions. Machate (2006) points out in his dissertation that you can find primarily methods for creating roadmaps for companies and institutes (research institutions and universities). However, there are a number of roadmaps about specific technologies in relation to regions, such as energy roadmaps on the European level, mobility roadmaps, an Austrian roadmap for high performance metals, and more. It should only be pointed out here that, very often, specific applications can be found at the national or international level, even though the methodology for creating roadmaps for a specific technology in connection with a region or country has not yet been described in a systematic and detailed manner. Of course, each roadmap for a specific technology related to a specific region or country requires a different approach. Nevertheless, there are core elements and project steps that are inherent in the roadmap and should not be missing. A good approach for this is e.g. "Energy Technology Roadmaps. A guide to development and implementation" (International Energy Agency, 2014).

The roadmapping process in DigiTeRRI develops one roadmap for each of the three territories – Grand Est in France, Värmland in Sweden, and Styria in Austria. As already described in section 2.3, such innovation ecosystems consist of actors from the quadruple helix (see **Figure 3**). Therefore (and because of RRI considerations), DigiTeRRI develops the roadmaps in a co-creation stakeholder process and brings together stakeholders from all 4H categories. As DigiTeRRI decided to co-create roadmaps with an RRI approach, the RRI process dimensions and the RRI normative framework play a core role in this process.

3.1.2 Roadmapping in DigiTeRRI generally

The main DigiTeRRI roadmap process is based on a classical roadmap process. It is a four-phase process, composed by the four phases of stocktaking and mapping, visioning, working out the roadmap development, and implementation and improvement. First, a common understanding among the participating stakeholders across the involved territories is required with respect to the overall process and the analytical frame. Based on that, territory-specific activities will be conducted.

Source: Own representation (AIT)

Figure 5: The DigiTeRRI roadmap procedure.

Phase A: Stocktaking / Mapping

The mapping of R&I ecosystems constitutes the basis for obtaining a comprehensive structural picture of the R&I landscapes of the territories under consideration. Methodologically, we employ a social network perspective to map the ecosystems, using systematic and large-scale databases of R&I activities. The social network perspective views the territories as a collection of nodes (organisations) that are inter-linked by edges (knowledge interactions of different kinds). By this we can infer the structure of the R&I ecosystems, as well as the role and positioning of individual organisations (e.g. who are the key players in certain fields). The main outcome of this step is (1) a structural view of the actor-topic landscape in a territory, (2) identification of existing development policies and planning tools to enhance the R&I ecosystems, and (3) identification of key R&I actors and stakeholders to support appropriate engaging strategies. The mapping is presented in the form of descriptive measures, but most importantly in the form of comparable network visualisations, based on spring model-inspired algorithms available in social network analytical software, where nodes (organisations) with their inter-linkages are positioned nearer to each other with increasing interaction intensity. This phase was implemented in WP2 of DigiTeRRI.

Phase B: Visioning

The implementation of the RRI approach for transitioning traditional industry territories into digitalized industry territories requires a vision. Framework and mapping are starting points for developing the vision by each territory's key R&I actors in stakeholder workshops (approximately 20 participants per workshop). Each workshop comprises the following steps:

- Step 1: Getting the workshop participants acquainted with the mapping results and the framework developed in WP2. This serves to create awareness.
- Step 2: Stimulating forward thinking by anticipating the future, using results from phase A.
- Step 3: Each participant formulates the future for him or herself, taking into account the question words *what*, *for whom*, and *how*.
- Step 4: Participants work in pairs to produce a common formulation based on the individual formulations from the previous step, taking into account the question words *what*, *for whom*, and *how*.
- Step 5: The pairs formed in the previous step join together to form groups of 4 persons each. Each group works out a common formulation based on the formulations in the previous step, taking into account the question words *what*, *for whom*, and *how*.
- Step 6: All the groups join together to create one common formulation on a flip chart, taking into account the question words *what*, *for whom*, and *how*.

This phase is implemented in WP3 of DigiTeRRI.

Phase C: Working out the roadmap

Good preparation for the workshops is indispensable for success. The structure for covering all necessary aspects has to be prepared. The visualisation design has to be developed, which depends on the specifics of digitalisation and on the territories (see chapter 3.1.4 on roadmap structure). The roadmap sphere of activities has to be defined beforehand. These are the tasks in phase C:

- Collecting the sphere of activities in the group using moderation cards. The vision is the ultimate goal.
- The development of the dependencies of the action fields in the individual roadmap sphere is a second task in the workshop. Which dependencies of which fields of action can be identified?

- Development of measures and action plan: What needs to be done so that the objectives can be achieved? Concrete measures and an action plan comprising resources, schedule, and people in charge will be defined.

This phase will be implemented in WP4 of DigiTeRRI.

Phase D: Implementation and improvement

The coordinator of each territory is in charge of implementing the measures defined in phase C. This implementation needs to be supported by highly expert task leaders equipped with the necessary soft skills. The implementation of the measures is monitored using the mapping in step 2. Based on the outcome of the monitoring, the framework and measures are improved. The transnational exchange of best practices will be conducted with all three territories. This phase will be implemented in WP5 of DigiTeRRI.

3.1.3 RRI-oriented roadmapping

Since RRI takes into account the effects and potential impacts of scientific research and technological development processes on the environment and society, DigiTeRRI engages important stakeholders who are affected by the digital transition process of a territory. The roadmap process itself is as important as the resulting document. Such a process involves and aligns various stakeholders in a common approach. While stakeholders work together towards common goals, the process creates new relationships that have a significant and lasting impact and support the implementation of the roadmap.

An effective roadmapping process engages stakeholders in a way so that it creates a plan and a consensus and increases the likelihood of implementation of the roadmap priorities. A dynamic roadmap process does not stop when the document is published. The frequency with which a roadmap is updated largely depends on the time frame considered. Usually roadmaps are updated regularly, approximately every five years. However, there are cases where roadmaps are updated more frequently to reflect the progress, the changes in available resources, or planning considerations.

Hence, DigiTeRRI integrates four RRI process dimensions throughout the roadmapping process:

- *Diverse & inclusive*: Actors and representative from all four quadruple helix categories are engaged in the whole roadmapping process from the early beginning, because they develop their own future in the co-creation process.

- *Anticipative & reflective*: Since roadmapping is a methodology for creating future orientation, this process is anticipative. We start with an analysis and discussion of the current situation. Based on that, each next step is discussed together with the stakeholders and adjusted. The various workshops allow feedback loops (reflection).
- *Open & transparent*: Since all relevant stakeholders of a territory are engaged, the process is open and transparent. Additionally, the main results of the roadmap are made public on the DigiTeRRI website.
- *Responsive & adaptive to change*: The starting point is the mapping and analysis. Therefore, DigiTeRRI reacts to the current situation. Several workshops over a time period of approximately 18 months make the process adaptive to change.

Furthermore, the RRI keys (described in section 2.5) play an important role in this roadmapping process. The role of the RRI keys in digitalization will be elaborated in section 3.2.

3.1.4 Roadmap structure and roadmap domains for digitalisation

The development of a roadmap requires an appropriate structure in which goals, tasks, measures, and action fields are considered. For which domains and categories will the stakeholders develop goals and actions? These domains and categories are strongly linked to the innovation ecosystem and the digitalisation process. An innovation ecosystem consists of a variety of actors, each belonging to one of the four generic actor types described by the quadruple helix. Such an innovation ecosystem is complex, and the actors interact in a way that cannot be predicted (see chapter 2.3).

There is a literature on the digitalization of companies and organisations. For instance, Bumann and Peter (2019) have analysed many studies and worked out six fields that should be considered for the digitalisation change process. These six fields are: (1) strategy, (2) organisation, (3) culture, (4) technology, (5) customers, (6) people. This study provides a basis for adaptation in DigiTeRRI. DigiTeRRI deals with the digitalisation of regions. This means the consideration goes far beyond the study of Bumann and Peter, who focus on organisations.

DigiTeRRI distinguishes between structural characteristics on the one hand and people/actors on the other. The structural characteristics should cover all action fields necessary for the transition into a digitalized region. The challenge is, however, to describe them at the same level of consideration. Based on this reflection and several workshops inside the DigiTeRRI consortium, DigiTeRRI has come up with the following seven domains as a proposal for the action fields:

1. Knowledge & skills
2. Technology
3. Networks & collaboration
4. Infrastructure
5. Culture & values
6. Leadership, business & market
7. Communication

Source: Own representation (AIT).

Figure 6. The seven roadmap domains for DigiTeRRI.

Since the development of a roadmap for digitalisation is a strategic action, the domain “strategy” is excluded here. The domain “culture & values” also includes ethics. Ethics plays a very important role in digitalisation. Since ethics is closely linked to values and culture, it is considered within this domain along with norms and standards. The domain “leadership, business & market” will address (i) how taking over the lead for a specific direction in digitalisation might be a good opportunity for a firm or a university, because there is already specific expertise in e.g. paper industry, (ii) also the necessity of the development of new business and business models (also for the government regarding e-government). Communication is not addressed in other studies. However, when dealing with a territory comprising diverse actors, communication is important for keeping people informed as well as for the communication from e.g. a firm seeking to attract the best people from abroad.

These seven roadmap domains are also linked to studies such as Peter et al. (2020), or the Digitalization Strategy – Lower Austria (2020) and Digital transition action plan (2018). The defined action in these studies supported covering all necessary aspects for the following matrix.

The following figure summarises these seven domains which are embedded into the actors’ system of the territory.

KNOWLEDGE & SKILLS

Acquiring new skills for dealing with all the devices and tools for processing digital actions is very highly required. Knowledge and skills must be developed for the understanding of digitalised processes and technology. Training and labs for gaining experience with the new subjects are necessary. Therefore, knowledge and skills for all generations of people have to be developed. This should also address creating awareness for digitalisation.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- Which knowledge and skills have to be developed and improved, and by whom?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

TECHNOLOGY

There are already big players on the globe, such as Google. Also, blockchain technology is a revolution. The question is how to get access to this technology. On the other hand, when it comes to specific industrial solutions, there is still a lot of potential for development. The technology domain addresses development of technology in the territory (e.g. specific technology for digitalisation in a specific industrial sector), availability of technology, or access to technology.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- Which technology is needed, and how can the actors of the territory get access to it?
- Which specific technology for digitalisation is not yet available, and what potential exists in the territory for the development of such technology?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

NETWORK & COLLABORATION

Formal and informal exchange and institutional networks play an important role in innovation. Collaboration is the action of working with someone to produce something. Collaboration also creates knowledge flow between actors. Examples are collaboration between digital twin developers and universities, collaboration between universities in the territory and research institutes, and technology providers in all parts of the world.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- Which collaboration or networks are necessary for the actors in the territory so that they can manage the transition into a digitalised territory?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

INFRASTRUCTURE

Infrastructure is a key success factor for a territory. It refers to basic physical and organizational structures and facilities. It comprises buildings, roads, trains, highways, plane connections, energy supplies, etc. Infrastructure is needed for the operation of a society or an enterprise. When considering digitalisation, broadband and 5G technologies emerge as important infrastructure elements.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- Which kind of infrastructure does the territory need for digitalisation?
- Which knowledge and skills have to be developed and improved, and by whom?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

CULTURE & VALUES

Culture can be described as the collective programming of the mind. Culture consists of patterns, explicit and implicit, of and for behaviour. The essential core of culture consists of traditional ideas and especially their attached values. Ethics deals with the foundation of human values, norms, customs, and moral concepts and aims to provide guidance on correct action. Central problems of ethics concern the motives, methods, and consequences of human action.

Being open for adapting to change reflects a part of the culture. Regarding digitalisation, one might notice that people in the territory use innovative digital tools and products in their everyday life, including in their leisure time (e.g. playing games online, or watching movies on Netflix together in a group).

Organisations, companies, and communities face the challenge of how to manage the transition into a digitalised environment.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- What is needed for changing the culture so that digitalisation is possible?
- How will a territory deal with digitalization from an ethical point of view?
- Which norms are needed?
- How can the change in the direction of digitalisation be organised?
- Which guidance will support the effort to meet the defined values?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

LEADERSHIP, BUSINESS & MARKET

Is there a company with a leadership in a specific technology (in our case digitalization)? This domain covers how organisations (all four types of actors of the quadruple helix) take over leadership of the transition into a digitalised territory.

Leadership, business & market addresses the possibilities for digital business models and new markets abroad. The business performance might be improved through digitalisation.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- How can leadership for a specific orientation regarding digitalisation be achieved?
- Which business models have to be developed for gaining success?
- How can the market be expanded through digitalisation?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

COMMUNICATION

Communication is the exchange of information by speaking, writing, or using some other medium.

Communication is the action of transferring information from one place, person, or group to another.

Communication inside the territory about all activities with regard to digitalisation is important so that as many inhabitants as possible are informed. Marketing campaigns will be necessary for attracting the best people for firms and universities. Communication is also necessary for gaining visibility in specific communities around the world.

The following questions should be considered during the roadmap development:

- How can the communication be organised so that all people affected in the territory are informed well enough about digitalisation and its advantages?
- How can the territory attract the best people from around the world to work in the territory?
- What needs to be communicated to the citizens in the territory so that they are well informed?
- What are the goals, for whom, and until when, considering the representatives of the quadruple helix?

D3.2 – Framework for RRI implementation in R&I ecosystems of the three territories
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The following table presents examples for goals for roadmap domains with actors of the quadruple helix.

Table 1: Matrix of goals for roadmap domains with actors of the quadruple helix – examples.

The road-map domains		Quadruple helix actors			
		Industry & business	Science & research	Government & public admin.	Civil society
1.	Knowledge & skills	E.g.: 30 new apprenticeships in industry created by Feb. 2022.	E.g.: A course in digital engineering for the steel industry is implemented by June 2022.	E.g.: All community workers are familiar with the current digital systems by the end of Sep. 2021.	E.g.: Courses for dealing with social media are offered in at least 70% of the communities in the territory by the end of Oct. 2021.
2.	Technology	E.g.: Blockchain technologies are adapted for SMEs by July 2022.	E.g.: A specific digital methodology and tools for the paper industry are developed by May 2022.	E.g.: Accelerate and adopt this specific digital emerging technology X in the following cities (A, B, C, D).	E.g.: The best available connectivity (5G) is implemented by Nov 2021.
3.	Networks & collaboration	E.g.: 5 networks with the 5 best organisation developing digital tools for the steel industry is established by June 2022.	E.g.: The universities, colleges, and research organisations in the region have established strategic collaboration with MIT.	E.g.: The communities in the territory have implemented collaboration with research organisations by Jan 2022.	E.g.: Regular round table discussions starting Sep. 2021.
4.	Infrastructure	E.g.: High-speed broadband works.	E.g.: A lab for by Oct. 2021.	E.g.: The best high-speed broadband is implemented by Oct. 2021.	E.g.: 90% of all citizens in the territory have access to high-speed broadband by the end of 2021.
5.	Culture & values	E.g.: (a) A concept for ethics in digitalisation is developed by Aug. 2021. (b) A plan regarding customer centricity is provided by March 2022.	E.g.: University X develops a plan for a change management for digitalisation (how to operationalise digitalisation in society) by June 2021.	E.g.: Development of a plan for user-centricity (i.e. online services need to be designed and provisioned considering a citizen perspective and not an administration perspective).	E.g.: How to attract candidates for particular tasks in digitalisation. Attract women in technical skills (50:50 female-male by end of 2022). A plan for changing of "culture" for attracting female talent is ready by June 2021.

The road-map domains		Quadruple helix actors	Industry & business	Science & research	Government & public admin.	Civil society
6.	Leadership (business & market)		E.g.: Development of specific business model (by use of digital sale) is developed by the end of 2021.	E.g.: The university Y focuses on the development of digital technology for the paper industry and attracts the best from all over the world (by June 2022).	E.g.: The Chamber of Commerce starts an initiative that makes the region play a pioneering role in digitization.	E.g.: High quality of life concept is developed by Aug. 2021.
7.	Communication		E.g.: Developing a marketing concept for attracting engineers for digitalisation of the processes.	E.g.: Developing a marketing campaign for attracting the best students is implemented by Dec 2021.	E.g.: Communicating how easy it is to use e-government.	E.g.: (a) Developing a communication platform for knowledge exchange in the population. (b) Developing a plan for an awareness campaign for civil society leadership (initiatives).

A roadmap contains goals in specific categories and time schedules within the action fields presented above. The basis for the goals is the common vision (which will be developed in workshop 1 in each territory) as a roadmap contains a clear statement of the desired outcome. There is a pathway for reaching it, which follows the roadmap logic with key elements below (see **Table 2** for description of key elements and **Figure 7** for a visual presentation).

Table 2: Description of key elements of a successful roadmap.

The goals: The goals are a clear and concise set of targets that, if achieved, will result in the desired outcome. The goals are quantified goals (e.g. “all municipalities in the territory have high-speed internet by end of 2022”). The quantified goals provide the most specific guidance.

Milestones: Milestones are interim performance targets for achieving the goals with specific dates (e.g. “50% of the municipalities will have built the hardware for high-speed internet by Oct. 2021”).

Gaps and barriers: The roadmapping process will detect a list of potential gaps in knowledge, technology limitations, market, structural barriers, regulatory limitations, public acceptance, or other barriers to achieving the goals and milestones.

Action items: The actions are developed to overcome any gaps or barriers. Actions are measures to overcome obstacles, to pave the way for achieving the goals. Typical solution actions include technology development, development of regulations and standards, policy agendas, creation of financing mechanisms, and public engagement.

Priorities and timelines: The actions will be prioritised with timelines. The most important actions that need to be taken in order to achieve the goals and the time frames will be specified. There will be interconnections among those actions. These interconnections have to be carefully considered with regard to the affected stakeholder roles and relationships.

This table is heavily inspired by International Energy Agency (2014) but contextualized for the DigiTeRRI project.

A roadmap should provide the ability to relink each project or activity using this logical structure to understand how the activity will ultimately help to achieve the roadmap goals. The real measure of success is whether or not the roadmap is implemented and achieves the desired outcome.

Source: Own representation (AIT) inspired by International Energy Agency (2014).

Figure 7: The logic of a roadmap.

The definitions of each element can be found in **Table 2**; the “Tasks” element will be defined in the roadmapping process itself.

3.2. The consequences of digitalization for RRI

In deliverable D2.4, a basic model of digital maturity was presented in which five different stages of digital maturity were distinguished. In this section we use a similar framework to analyse the relationship between RRI and digitalization, but for simplicity we focus only on the contrast between the extreme endpoints of digitalization, i.e. “low” and “high” levels of digitalization, corresponding to the traditional industry state and the fully digitalized state. The RRI implications at intermediary stages of digitalization are a combination of the RRI implications at the extreme points, so we believe there is no reason to address them separately.

Our model focuses attention on how RRI opportunities and challenges change as the regions and the organizations within them are transformed from a non-digital to a digital state of development. In other words,

there is an *implicit process* or a *set of implicit processes* which will move organizations from a low level of digitalization maturity to a high level. These processes will be developed in the roadmapping process itself. The overarching theme that emerges from the framework is that while RRI opportunities and challenges are fairly easy to manage in a low-digitalization scenario, digital transformation greatly increases the number and complexity of the RRI opportunities and challenges that regional R&I actors must contend with.

Since stakeholders must take RRI into account when co-creating their territorial roadmaps, the outline of non-region-specific RRI-related challenges and opportunities in the present deliverable provides them with a useful checklist for identifying relevant RRI-related challenges and opportunities in their own territory. The framework is structured by the five RRI “keys” defined by the European Commission: ethics, gender equality, open access, public engagement, and science education (see section 2.5). In the following subsections the five keys are discussed in turn. **Table 3** at the end of the section summarizes the RRI challenges and opportunities associated with low and high levels of digitalization, respectively.

ETHICS

In the low-digitalization organization, many ethical considerations are relatively simple. For example, data security and privacy issues barely arise if the organization does not store or manipulate personal data to any significant extent. On the other hand, the lack of a digital infrastructure makes it difficult for such an organization to be transparent, since it only has a limited amount of data available about its own activities. Besides, the organization may lack the data necessary to make well-informed decisions on ethical matters. For example, managers might not be aware of systematic discrimination in the workplace that arises as a consequence of seemingly benign routines and practices (Pauline. T. Kim, 2018).

As an organization becomes more digitally mature, transparency becomes easier as the organization can share more data and increase the traceability of its own actions, e.g. by means of blockchain technology and “smart contracts”. It also becomes easier for the organization to discover previously hidden internal ethical problems, e.g. patterns of systemic discrimination.

At the same time, digitalization brings new challenges with regard to safeguarding privacy and security. Once data is digitized, it typically becomes easier to steal from remote locations. ICT infrastructure is increasingly transferred to the cloud, i.e. outsourced to third-party service providers, which presents a major challenge to privacy as the data hosted through such services is subject to the jurisdiction of the states in which it is stored. Outsourcing of data management also creates a risk that third parties will sell the data to other organizations. Although digitalization may increase transparency in principle, high data complexity may reduce de facto transparency as it can become nearly impossible for non-specialists to fully understand the data. If specialized

knowledge is needed to manage and interpret the data, and if this knowledge is possessed only by a small number of individuals, the RRI principle of inclusivity is jeopardized.

GENDER EQUALITY

Although the principle of gender equality promotes the equality of all genders, discussions of gender equality tend to focus on securing equality for women, who are often perceived to be in a disadvantaged position vis-à-vis men in a variety of contexts, not least in the labour market. Accordingly, while our analysis in this subsection addresses gender equality in general, we will pay particular attention to the issue of equality for women.

One key characteristic of organizations with a low level of digitalization is that they are not dependent to any significant extent on ICT staff to stay in operation. This can be considered an advantage from the point of view of gender equality since, statistically speaking, ICT specialists are predominantly men. According to a report by the OECD, in 2015 the proportion of female ICT specialists in the G20 economies ranged between 13% and 32%.⁴

On the other hand, digitalization also brings a number of opportunities related to gender equality. Organizations with a high need for ICT expertise may actively recruit female ICT specialists and thus make a contribution to narrowing the gender gap in this profession. High digital competency at the organizational level also means better access to data and statistics on gender-related issues within the organization and in the surrounding ecosystem. Digital tools can help organizations target women in outreach activities and recruitment. Digitalization opens up opportunities for working remotely and thus expands the talent pool available for recruitment, making it easier to maintain a diverse workforce.

These opportunities are accompanied by significant challenges. With regard to recruitment of ICT professionals, since the pool of female talent is limited, intense competition among employers who wish to increase workplace diversity makes it difficult to achieve gender balance outside of the most attractive companies. A more subtle challenge involves gender bias in digital tools. Just as algorithms can be tuned to target women and promote female participation, they can also potentially be biased against women, sometimes in ways that are not obvious to their users (M. Kim, 2018). Even algorithms that do favour women (e.g. for recruitment purposes) might be biased against particular ethnicities or other sub-groups of women (Ruberg & Ruelos, 2020; Saka, 2020; Welles, 2014), which opens an additional layer of ethical complexity. Another ethical and legal dilemma relates to the privacy of data: keeping track of detailed gender-related information might violate privacy rights.

⁴ <http://www.oecd.org/digital/bridging-the-digital-gender-divide.pdf>

Another important aspect of gender equality and digitalization was highlighted by Carli (2020) in her review of how COVID-19 has affected gender equality. She points out that during the pandemic, women whose jobs are digitalized tend to be affected differently by the COVID-19 crisis than their male counterparts. There are two reasons why this is the case: women are more likely to shoulder childcare work and other household responsibilities while simultaneously being expected to work from home. While schools and kindergartens shut down due to COVID-19 infection spikes, childcare and work obligations will likely interfere with each other, putting, on average, a greater burden on women. Carli (2020) does, however, point out that there may be a silver lining to this story: as men telecommute more, they take a more active role in childcare which might increase their long-term participation in raising their children.

The analysis in this subsection indicates that the transition from a low to high digitalization maturity level brings with it a number of new challenges, but also opportunities, for gender equality.

OPEN ACCESS

It is possible for organizations characterized by a low level of digitalization to pursue an open access data policy, but in practice such organizations are limited to granting open access to simple documents, either in print or digital form, limited in number and with few customization or interactivity features. The advantage of being subject to such constraints is that there is no need for the organization to grapple with complex issues related to data management and intellectual property rights.

Digitalization greatly expands the amount of data an organization can make available to the public through online channels. This applies to raw data as well as collations of data. Data visualization becomes far easier and potentially more powerful, enabling clear communication of facts and ideas to potential users of the data. While this is enticing from an RRI perspective, it also creates pitfalls that an organization committed to open access must carefully navigate.

High levels of data complexity make data sharing costly – not only in terms of hosting costs and other direct expenses but also with regard to the costs of ensuring that the data is accurate, that collated data provides a correct picture of reality, etc. The legal costs of making data public can also be prohibitive, for example because of IPR restrictions. For many data types it is legally problematic to share data with actors outside one's own country or outside the EU. Many organizations must keep some data non-open due to its sensitivity and the loss of value that would be incurred if the data were made available to competitors. Since data is critically important to the value creation processes of a digitalized organization, decisions regarding open access to data must be deliberated carefully.

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

When it comes to public engagement, organizations with a low level of digitalization will by necessity be focused on face-to-face interaction with the public. In one way this may be viewed as an advantage since personal, face-to-face communication is considered by some to be more effective and more conducive to establishing trust than online communication. Such benefits are disputed, however, and recently the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed a new, previously disregarded challenge in face-to-face engagement: disease transmission risk. What is not in dispute is that public engagement in a physical forum is costly and subject to geographical and logistical limitations.

Digitalization brings possibilities for online public engagement activities, which are cheaper to organize and attend and can potentially reach wider segments of the public than traditional location-bound events. In particular, members of the public who live in isolated areas or in areas with poor transportation infrastructure stand to benefit from the digital transformation. Digitalization also makes it easier for organizations to gather data about public opinion on specific issues as well as other information about the public that is relevant for planning public engagement activities.

These potential advantages of digitalization for public engagement come with several caveats. While digital technologies make it easier to engage most groups of individuals, the opposite may be the case for certain groups. Recently there has been an outcry among senior citizens who are not comfortable with newer forms of communication. Digitalization optimists might say that this is only a passing problem, but on the other hand it would be naive to think that new generations will be able to stay on top of all future communications technology developments. Anyone with a responsibility for public engagement should carefully consider the possibility that they might be excluding some groups of individuals by employing modern technologies. Furthermore, while digitalization facilitates the dissemination of information, it does the same for disinformation. Groups of individuals who have something to gain by swaying public opinion may try to take advantage of online public engagement venues to disseminate false information in support of their cause. This issue is particularly pertinent when public forums are used since the moderation of such forums is highly resource-demanding. However, disinformation does not necessarily come from outside groups hijacking public digital venues. The organizers of public events can potentially use digital tools to peddle false narratives themselves – and have a responsibility not to do so.

SCIENCE EDUCATION

Low-digitalization organizations wishing to undertake science education activities have no choice but to rely on traditional methods of education such as face-to-face student-teacher interaction. The advantage of these methods is that they have been tested through long practice. There is a wealth of accumulated experience for educators to draw on, and students know what they will get. The drawbacks are similar to those mentioned in the section on public engagement above: access to students is constrained by geographical and logistical limitations. Moreover, students living in more affluent areas are more likely to receive high-quality education, which contradicts the inclusivity principle of RRI.

Digitalization enables educators to increase their geographical reach using digital tools. As online solutions to education become more prominent, it becomes easier for individuals outside central regions to obtain high-quality education without having to move away from their home region. This has the added benefit of helping to curb depopulation in vulnerable areas. Organizations that are not primarily focused on education but have a high level of digital maturity can also take part in education activities themselves, increasing the relevance of education for industry. Such activities can also act as a platform for recruitment.

On the other hand, with greater reach comes greater responsibility. As online tools provide educators with a global reach and allow them to connect with ever more diverse groups of students, it becomes critical for educators to think carefully about how the knowledge they disseminate can be interpreted, used, and abused.

Table 3: RRI challenges and opportunities; keys in alphabetical order.

Digitalization maturity level		
Low		High
Ethics		
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Security and privacy issues are simple 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Potential for improved transparency in general ▪ Blockchain technology and "smart" contracts can improve transparency and traceability in business and logistics
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Difficult to be transparent because of limited availability of data to make public ▪ Lack of information to inform ethical decisions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Hard to safeguard privacy, security, safety ▪ Must rely on third-party vendors (e.g., for data storage) ▪ High data complexity reduces de facto transparency ▪ More information means greater responsibility ▪ Actors may sell information to third parties

Digitalization maturity level

Gender equality

Opportunities

- Easier to achieve a high proportion of female staff (because of lower need for ICT specialists, who tend to be men)
- Easier to target specific genders in outreach, recruitment, and education
- Easier to compile data and statistics related to gender
- Remote work allows greater diversity, incl. gender diversity
- Opportunity to recruit and promote female ICT specialists

Challenges

- Hard to compile data and statistics related to gender
- Greater need for hiring ICT experts, who are predominantly men
- Danger of gender bias in algorithms

Digitalization maturity level

Open access

Opportunities

- Low data complexity makes it simple to manage an open access policy
- Vast possibilities for making data available to the public online

Challenges

- Few means of making data available to the public
- Complex data makes open access costly
- Complex decisions about which data to make public
- Complex, costly IPR and other legal issues (licenses, etc.)
- Cross-border data transfers have legal and political implications

Digitalization maturity level

Public engagement

Opportunities

- Face-to-face outreach stimulates engagement
- Specific interest groups can be targeted more precisely
- Easy to gather data about the public and their interests
- Public events can be held online, at low cost and with wide reach

Challenges

- Access to the public limited by geography, logistics
- Epidemic outbreaks can make face-to-face engagement hazardous to participants
- Risk of missing the broader public in favor of specific groups
- Harder to engage senior citizens and other groups with low digital competence
- Risk of activities getting hijacked by delegitimate groups
- Easier to falsify narratives

Digitalization maturity level

Science education

Opportunities

- Well-tested, traditional educational tools
- Digital tools increase geographical reach
- A digitalized organization can easily take part in education activities (and teach digitalization to others)
- Science education can be used for recruitment purposes

Challenges

- Access to students limited by geography and logistics
- With greater reach comes greater responsibility

4. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This deliverable lays out a non-region-specific framework for digitalization at the regional level under consideration of RRI principles. Going forward, the framework will be used in DigiTeRRI for several purposes:

- The framework helps create a shared understanding among territories and partners in DigiTeRRI about roadmapping methodology, regional transition processes, and the relationship between RRI and digitalization.
- The framework will be used in communicating with the stakeholders in regional workshops about the roadmapping process and how to take RRI into account in digitalization.
- The present deliverable helps the consortium convey the aims and methods of DigiTeRRI to the European Commission.

The common framework introduced in this report consists of two parts. In the first part we explain DigiTeRRI's roadmapping methodology at a conceptual level, setting the stage for creating actual roadmaps in the three pilot territories of DigiTeRRI in WP4. In the second part we describe at a non-region-specific level how the transition from a traditional industry region to a digitalized region creates challenges and opportunities for practicing RRI.

The main DigiTeRRI roadmap process is based on a classical roadmap process and is composed of four phases: stocktaking and mapping; visioning; roadmap development; and roadmap implementation and improvement. The methodology revolves around co-creation with stakeholders, and therefore achieving a common understanding among the participating stakeholders with respect to the overall process and the analytical frame is an essential prerequisite for success. Throughout the roadmapping process, DigiTeRRI integrates the major process dimensions of RRI: diversity and inclusiveness; anticipation and reflexivity; openness and transparency; and responsiveness and adaptivity. The roadmapping process generates action plans for each of the four types of stakeholders that together compose the “quadruple helix”: government, academia, industry, and civil society.

The second part of the framework analyses the relationship between RRI and digitalization, focusing for simplicity on the contrast between the extreme endpoints of digitalization, i.e. “low” digitalization (traditional industry) and “high” digitalization (fully digitalized R&I ecosystem). This part of the framework shows how RRI opportunities and challenges change as regions and the organizations within them are transformed from a non-digital to a digital state of development. The analysis is structured by the five RRI “keys” highlighted by the

European Commission as being of particular practical importance: gender equality, public engagement, open access, science education, and ethics. The overarching theme that emerges from the analysis is that while RRI opportunities and challenges are fairly easy to manage in a low-digitalization scenario, digital transformation greatly increases the number and complexity of the RRI opportunities and challenges with which regional R&I actors must contend.

Additionally, in this deliverable we provide up-to-date background knowledge concerning key concepts and trends that underpin the common framework. Specifically, we discuss regional transition processes; the role of Smart Specialisation in regional policy; sustainable R&I ecosystems; digitalization; and responsible research and innovation (RRI). These sections also serve to provide a shared knowledge base and vocabulary for DigiTeRRI partners to use within the project.

The common framework presented in this deliverable synthesizes relevant literature as well as findings from previous DigiTeRRI deliverables to ensure synergy and coherence within the project. The description of the roadmapping methodology refers back to the ecosystem mapping and stocktaking work carried out in WP2, adding clarity to how the ecosystem mapping fits into the overall methodology of DigiTeRRI. Looking forward, the framework will serve as an input to WP4, where the roadmapping methodology outlined in this deliverable will be applied in practice to the three pilot territories of DigiTeRRI. The framework will also help participants at the workshops in WP4 gain a better understanding of how they can shape the future of their own region. Since stakeholders must take RRI into account when co-creating their territorial roadmaps, the outline of non-region-specific RRI-related challenges and opportunities in the present deliverable provides them with a useful checklist for identifying relevant RRI-related challenges and opportunities in their own territory.

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